

1 **Supplementary Materials for**
2 **Multivariable Integrated Evaluation of**
3 **GloSea5-GC2 Ocean Hindcasting**

4
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0.6 0.65 0.7 0.75 0.8 0.85 0.9 0.95 1 1.05 1.1 1.15 1.2 1.25 1.3 1.35 1.4

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Fig. S1. Portrait diagram of the RMS for monthly anomalies of SST compared with EN4, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c) T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

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The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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Fig. S2. Portrait diagram of the RMS for monthly anomalies of SSS compared with EN4, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c) T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

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The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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39 **Fig. S3.** Portrait diagram of the RMS for monthly anomalies of SSC compared with
 40 SODA, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c)
 41 T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 42 ordinate indicate 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively. The averaged
 43 result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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47 **Fig. S4.** Portrait diagram of the RMS for monthly anomalies of SSH compared with
 48 SODA, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c)
 49 T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 50 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

51 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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54 **Fig. S5.** Portrait diagram of the CORR for monthly anomalies of SST compared with
 55 EN4, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c) T.
 56 Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 57 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

58 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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61 **Fig. S6.** Portrait diagram of the CORR for monthly anomalies of SSS compared with
 62 EN4, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c) T.
 63 Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 64 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.
 65 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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67 **Fig. S7.** Portrait diagram of the CORR for monthly anomalies of SSC compared with
 68 SODA, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c)
 69 T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 70 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

71 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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75 **Fig. S8.** Portrait diagram of the CORR for monthly anomalies of SSH compared with
 76 SODA, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c)
 77 T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 78 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

79 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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82 **Fig. S9.** Portrait diagram of the RMSD for monthly anomalies of SST compared with
 83 EN4, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c) T.
 84 Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 85 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

86 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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90 **Fig. S10.** Portrait diagram of the RMSD for monthly anomalies of SSS compared with
 91 EN4, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c) T.
 92 Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 93 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

94 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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97 **Fig. S11.** Portrait diagram of the RMSD for monthly anomalies of SSC compared with
 98 SODA, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c)
 99 T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 100 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

101 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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105 **Fig. S12.** Portrait diagram of the RMSD for monthly anomalies of SSH compared with
 106 SODA, simulated by GloSea5 hindcasts from 1992–2009, for: (a) GLB, (b) N. Pac, (c)
 107 T. Pac, (d) S. Pac, (e) Ind, (f) SO, (g) N. Atl, (h) T. Atl, and (i) S. Atl. The abscissa and
 108 ordinate indicate initial field and 1–7 lead months and each initial month, respectively.

109 The averaged result (AVG) across the initial months is shown in the top line.

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